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Abstract

The effectiveness of English lessons in Azerbaijan has increased compared to previous years. In particular, the addition of listening texts to English exams is a welcome development. Thus, the expected result from the lessons is positive. Teachers use different methods and strategies to develop students' listening skills, which include intensive and extensive listening methods. Applying these methods, language learners fully understand the listening text, and in addition, they become familiar with new vocabulary and grammatical rules. Many linguists have conducted research to improve listening skill. According to Harmer, the teacher's use of materials has a significant impact on the development of listening skill. In general, the development of listening skill is not expected only from teachers. For this, students should prepare a self-development plan and seriously prepare to achieve a goal. Listening skill is one of the four main skills in English. Despite the development of modern technologies, there are still difficulties for students in mastering this skill. This, in turn, is due to the sounds that are not in Azerbaijani, but are processed interdentally in English, which is reflected in the article. In addition, teachers' bottom-up and top-down teaching strategies facilitate the development of this skill in a short time.

Keywords: teacher, student, listening skills, strategy, development

Introduction

Like all other languages, English is learned during the process of listening, speaking, reading and writing [2]. To learn any language, first of all, listening skill needs to be instilled and developed. It is known that every person listens to people around them from birth, imitates them and finally begins to speak. It is usually implemented through Audio-visual method [3]. This process is the same in English, as in any language. It is absurd to be able to learn English only through grammar and vocabulary, because during real communication it is necessary to understand what the speaker is saying. Therefore, making the listening process a habit for language learners is one of the main conditions. Most language learners find listening difficult, which in turn is due to the fact that listening is not taught properly. There are some important techniques for this that all teachers and students should know and use [6].

Listening plays an important role in everyday life, and when people communicate, 9% is spent on writing, 16% on reading, 30% on speaking, and 45% on listening, which shows the importance of listening in the communication process [1]. Listening is the first skill that emerges. Listening skill can be developed in different ways. Each teacher has their own unique teaching style. Most teachers use listening texts available in books during their teaching. The vocabulary in these texts is given in advance to students to familiarize them with the listening section [4].

Methodology

It is necessary to talk about the essence of the listening process, its organization and benefits. The listening process consists of 3 parts: pre-listening, during-listening and post-listening parts.

In the pre-listening part, the student is informed about the essence of listening. At that time, the teacher gives explanations such as what to pay more attention to, providing information on the topic with vocabulary, etc. During listening, the text is listened to and the

given tasks are completed. The post-listening part is very important for the student, because the teacher clarifies the parts that are incomprehensible to the student by explaining the mistakes made. This feedback should be done by all teachers [2]. In order to provide a clear explanation of the processes, various situations should be considered [5]. Situations improve listening types, and listening types improve language skills. Explaining listening types to students allows them to understand half of the listening task. Types of listening texts can be given in the following cases:

1) Broadcasting any news - During this listening text, certain political, economic, ecological, etc. information is given and students are required to complete tasks related to the text. At this time, it is necessary to find out when, how and why the event happened using "Wh" questions. In addition, the answers to these texts are also found by taking notes.

2) Directions to home - This is a way to find the correct answer using the first map or any pictures that come to mind at that time. That is, the student must do these tasks during this listening text. The above-mentioned note-taking may also be included in this.

3) Description of a missing person - Taking pictures and choosing one of the given pictures are the main tasks given in this listening text.

4) Telling a funny story - The requirement to present the pictures in the correct order, as well as answering questions using question words, are the characteristics of this type.

5) Shopping dialogue – This dialogue could be an example of a listening text between a salesperson and a customer. At that time, tasks are given with the help of "Wh" question words.

6) Music lyrics - This listening text may be the most favorite type of students. Because at that time, students have fun and learn. In the task given to song lyrics, filling in the gaps with the correct words, working with certain adjectives, and writing the gaps using

question words are the main tasks used in making this listening text.

7) Recorded entertainment information - This type includes texts about theater or movies. It is intended to do tasks such as filling in certain tables, writing accurate words, and taking notes.

8) Weather forecast - This type of listening text is both interesting and relatively confusing. At that time, tasks are given by giving question words, adjectives, and pictures.

Discussion of findings

Listening comprehension is useful for learners' pronunciation. That is, when students are exposed to spoken English more, they can know more and learn its tone, intonation, and accents. Other reasons for listening include gathering information, enjoying, agreeing, evaluating, and criticizing [7]. Another reason for listening is to improve speaking skill by improving pronunciation. Listening is not only a basic form of communication, but also helps the language learner to appreciate the beauty of the language. Especially in terms of teaching communicative language, it is said that listening is the basis of communicative competence because it provides aural input and allows learners to interact in spoken communication, and therefore, language learning depends largely on listening. Thus, listening is the concrete basis of complete language proficiency [8]. There are many reasons for listening. There are five main reasons for listening: engaging in social protocols, exchanging information, enjoying, sharing emotions, and controlling. Underwood (1989) stated that teachers should prepare their students for the following situations:

a. To participate in the lesson. The purpose of this activity is to understand the main ideas and recognize the main information.

b. Listening to announcements, news and weather forecasts. The main purpose of listeners is to obtain relevant information.

c. Listening to plays, watching television or listening to the radio for entertainment. The purpose of this activity is to entertain oneself

d. Listening to a speaker. In this case, the listener is interested in the speaker's ideas and attitudes.

e. Following instructions. The listener's purpose is to successfully perform the function.

In order to properly master the listening process, it is necessary to know listening strategies. Listening strategies are techniques or activities that directly help in remembering listening information. In recent days, a number of listening strategies have been developed according to each different listening situation, and therefore, by teaching listening skill, it is made easier for language learners to adapt their listening behaviors to deal with different situations, types of input and listening purposes. At this time, it becomes easier for the student to do the tasks.

Tyagi states that hearing is the perception of sound waves; to listen, you must first hear, but you do not need to listen to hear; to understand is to perceive the symbols we see and hear; to investigate the meaning of the stimuli we perceive; to remember is not only to receive and clarify the message, but also to add it to the

brain's reserve; to evaluate requires the active listener to weigh the evidence or to separate fact from opinion, the presence or absence of bias in the message; to respond requires the receiver to complete the process through verbal or non-verbal feedback [9].

Teachers have a great responsibility in their lessons and can have a great influence on their students in creating a friendly environment. Harmer notes that the main roles for teachers are:

- The teacher is the controller, he decides and controls what and how to do in the listening process.

- He is also the evaluator, providing students with feedback after listening.

- The teacher is the main resource, passing on information about unknown vocabulary and grammar that comes up after listening to students.

In addition, students can be more involved in the lesson by bringing a guest whose native language is English to the classroom. At that time, the communication between them creates an original listening. Before entering the classroom, the teacher gives the guest brief information about the students' language level and their ability to use the language, but invites them to communicate without straying from naturalness. The teacher and the guest enter the room together. The teacher does not tell the students anything about the identity of the guest and asks them to prepare interview-type questions. Then the students take notes and prepare various questions. The teacher turns on the recorder and begins the interview. Thus, the lesson is conducted both effectively and entertainingly.

Conclusion

Finally, it is possible to conclude that our country, Azerbaijan, has significantly improved the teaching of English. There are numerous methods and strategies for developing listening skill in students in English lessons. In these ways, students can be introduced to listening texts and further improve this skill in them. Basically, the student must know what he wants to do, have a goal for this and be able to implement it. On this path, the teacher is the main supporter of the student and can fully prepare the students both technically and morally. The development of modern technologies facilitates the teacher's work in this area.

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